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1 The GEOFON Program in 2020

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8 Abstract

9 The GEOFON program consists of a global seismic network, a seismological data center and a
10 global earthquake monitoring system. The seismic network has regional focus in Europe and
11 North Africa as well as around the Indian Ocean, but operates stations on all continents as well
12 as Greenland on the North American continental plate and Antarctica. The data center provides
13 real-time seismic data through SeedLink protocol and historical data from its large archive
14 comprising currently 120 TB of temporary and permanent seismic network data from GFZ and
15 third party partners made available via standard services as part of the European Integrated
16 Data Archive (EIDA) and within the International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks
17 (FDSN). GEOFON also provides global and rapid earthquake information. The rapid earthquake
18 information service prioritizes fast information dissemination after moderate and large
19 earthquakes globally, based on automatic processing. Most operations are carried out using the

20 SeisComP system. GEOFON distributes FAIR data, services, products and software free of charge
21 and are used worldwide by hundreds of users and other data centers.

22 [Introduction and historical overview](#)

23 For almost three decades the GEOFON program at the German Research Centre for Geosciences
24 (GFZ) in Potsdam (see Data and Resources) has operated both a global seismic network and a
25 seismological data center. Potsdam can be considered the birthplace of global instrumental
26 seismology for it was here at the Royal Prussian Geodetic Institute that in 1889 the first
27 documented recording of a teleseismic earthquake was made by Ernst von Rebeur-Paschwitz
28 with a pendulum horizontal seismometer, preceding a recording with an identical instrument in
29 Wilhelmshaven by a few tens of seconds (Rebeur-Paschwitz, 1889). This initial success led
30 Rebeur-Paschwitz as early as 1895 to propose a global network of seismometers to monitor
31 earthquakes. The era of modern broadband seismology started in the 1970s. In Germany, the
32 establishment of the Gräfenberg-Array (GRF) and the regional German network (GRSN),
33 operated by the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR) (Stammler et al.,
34 2020), set new standards for seismic monitoring at the global level by using the newly
35 developed high sensitivity broadband seismometers in combination with high resolution digital
36 signal processing technology.

37 Shortly after its creation in 1992, GFZ established the GEOFON program to carry on the tradition
38 of promoting global seismic monitoring and data exchange. The program evolved in synergy
39 with the seismological community with a clear commitment towards an open data policy as well
40 as fostering new standards in seismology right from its inception (Hanka and Kind, 1994).

41 Following these principles, GEOFON has fostered European cooperation in being one of the
42 founding members of the Observatories & Research Facilities for European Seismology
43 (ORFEUS, see Data and Resources). At the international level, the bilateral cooperation between
44 GEOFON and the Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology (IRIS, see Data and
45 Resources) in 1994 was the first step to open high-quality broadband data to the seismological
46 community, by means of the installation of a GOPHER node in Potsdam. GOPHER was the first
47 automated global data retrieval system initiated by IRIS in the early 90s. It was based on dialup
48 telephone lines connecting
49 to Data Request Manager (DRM) interfaces at the stations. Data retrieved by all GOPHER nodes
50 (e.g. IRIS, ORFEUS, Earthquake Research Institute of Tokyo) were available to the community a
51 few hours after an event occurred, which at that time represented a notable improvement over
52 the status quo in the early 1990s (Hanka and Kind, 1994). Later, GEOFON played a leading role in
53 the creation and development of the European Integrated Data Archive (EIDA), a group of data
54 centers within ORFEUS, which were technically interconnected by software developed at
55 GEOFON and deployed in cooperation with other European data centers, allowing users to
56 request data from any of the data centers in a transparent way without the need to know where
57 the data were hosted (van Eck et al., 2004; Strollo et al., this Issue).

58 There are major milestones to be mentioned in the history of GEOFON. First, the development
59 and community adoption of the SeedLink protocol (see Data and Resources) in the late 1990s,
60 which became a global de facto standard still in use today, allowed the real-time distribution of
61 data between networks and data centers. In the early 2000s, development of the Arclink
62 protocol (deprecated since 2019) was key to interconnecting the data archives of all EIDA data
63 centers, and was only recently superseded by the use of FDSN web services.

64 A pivotal moment was the 2004 Aceh-Andaman earthquake and tsunami, which prompted the
65 German government to fund the GITEWS project (German Indian Ocean Tsunami Early Warning
66 System) (Lauterjung et al. 2010). In this project, GEOFON was tasked to deliver a system capable
67 of rapidly locating and providing reliable magnitudes for potential tsunamigenic earthquakes for
68 Indonesia. The particular challenge was that a tsunami warning system for Indonesia had to be
69 not only effective for distant shores, the 'far-field' mode of operation for tsunami warning at the
70 time, but also in the 'near-field' where a tsunamigenic event has to be detected within a few
71 minutes of occurrence to notify nearby emergency service agencies in a timely manner. It
72 quickly became clear that rapid detection, location and non-saturating magnitude
73 determination of potentially tsunamigenic earthquakes was the only viable means to provide
74 tsunami warnings on such a short time scale. Seismological monitoring systems existing around
75 2005 did not meet the requirements for a modular, distributed processing based on standard
76 protocols. In addition, the seismic networks in operation at the time were woefully inadequate
77 for the rapid detection of offshore earthquakes in Indonesia and most of the Indian Ocean.
78 The GEOFON team coordinated the task of developing suitable software with the requirements
79 of the Indonesian government regarding early warning performance targets (Hanka et al., 2010).
80 The support by the GITEWS project led to the professionalization of software development at
81 GEOFON and the development of SeisComP (Hanka et al., 2003; Helmholtz Centre Potsdam GFZ
82 German Research Centre for Geosciences and gempa GmbH, 2008) as an integrated seismic
83 observatory software system enabling both the management of real-time seismic data flows as
84 well as the automatic or interactive detection, location and in-depth analysis of earthquakes. In
85 addition, GEOFON improved the seismic coverage in the Indian Ocean by establishing a
86 backbone seismic network for the Indonesian Tsunami Early Warning System (InaTEWS, see

87 Data and Resources) with additional stations in other countries around the Indian Ocean,
88 including Sri Lanka, Maldives, Yemen, Kenya and Madagascar. Besides two stations in Yemen
89 damaged by air strikes and lost due to the ongoing war, all GEOFON's other GITEWS stations are
90 currently in operation.

91 GEOFON is now positioned as one of the global reference scientific infrastructures in seismology
92 because of the continuous extension of its global seismic network, the ingestion of growing
93 amounts of data from partners into the data center, and the operation of a Rapid Earthquake
94 Monitoring System (see Data and Resources), which is based on SeisComP and focuses on
95 providing rapid location, magnitude and moment tensor information for large earthquakes
96 worldwide. Within the next sections we present the three main GEOFON components, namely,
97 the global seismic network, the data center, and the Rapid Earthquake Monitoring System as
98 well as some relevant software developments.

99 [The global seismic network](#)

100 The GEOFON global seismic network presently consists of 82 high quality stations (GEOFON Data
101 Centre, 1993). Operations started in 1993 with the installation of stations in Papua New Guinea
102 (Port Moresby, PMG, jointly operated with IRIS and the local Geophysical Observatory), in Czech
103 Republic (Moravsky Beroun, MORC, operated in cooperation with the local IPE-Brno and
104 Institute of Physics of the Czech Republic) and in Ireland (Dublin, DSB, operated in cooperation
105 with the Geophysics section of Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies), all are still in operation
106 today through long standing cooperation with local operators and other partners. The network
107 is among the largest global real-time seismic networks (e.g. GSN, Gee and Leith, 2011;
108 GEOSCOPE, Institut De Physique Du Globe De Paris (IPGP) & Ecole Et Observatoire Des Sciences

109 De La Terre De Strasbourg (EOST), 1982), providing valuable data for almost all seismological
110 research projects at GFZ and the wider seismological community. The GEOFON network is
111 operated jointly with more than 50 international partners with stations on all continents, but
112 concentrated in Europe and the Mediterranean region, as well as in the Indian Ocean (Figure
113 1a). Station operation is mostly performed by local partners with GFZ guidance and logistical
114 support, allowing the global network to be technically advanced and extremely cost-effective.
115 All stations are equipped with broadband sensors (Figure 1b); stations in regions prone to large
116 earthquakes are additionally equipped with strong-motion sensors (GEOFON Data Centre,
117 1993). This setup allows resolution of the complete seismic spectrum, from small high-
118 frequency local earthquakes to the largest global earthquakes. Recently, in collaboration with
119 the Geodesy department of the GFZ, we augmented selected stations with GNSS and
120 environmental sensors. One of the latest additions to the GEOFON network has been the new
121 Accra (ACRG) multiparametric station in Ghana, equipped with broadband and strong motion
122 sensors as well as GNSS and environmental sensors. The station was deployed during the GFZ
123 international Training Course (ITC, see Data and resources) in October 2018 and since then
124 successfully contributes to global monitoring filling a gap in the region. Data from all stations are
125 acquired using various communication types (VSAT, BGAN, UMTS, DSL, etc.), and also
126 distributed in real-time to earthquake monitoring and tsunami warning centers immediately
127 after acquisition. During 2019 more than 100 TB of real-time data were requested from the
128 GEOFON network (FDSN network code GE).

129 The data center

130 GEOFON operates the GFZ seismological data center, which facilitates real-time access to data
131 from the GEOFON stations and those of many partner networks and plate boundary
132 observatories, providing a secure long-term archive for seismological data.

133 GEOFON currently archives and distributes seismic data from 35 permanent networks and an
134 increasing number of temporary networks (114 in September 2020), including those from
135 seismological experiments carried out by scientists at German universities. It also serves as the
136 permanent archive for the passive component of the Geophysical Instrument Pool Potsdam
137 (GIPP) (Haberland and Ritter, 2016). A schematic view of the data center and its relation with
138 the other GEOFON components is provided in Figure 2.

139 GEOFON organizes the data exchange of real-time and archived data with international partner
140 institutions and earthquake centers. It also cooperates with them in the definition of standards
141 of seismological data exchange within the International Federation of Digital Seismograph
142 Networks (FDSN), ORFEUS and in the scope of bilateral initiatives (e.g. Quinteros et al., this
143 issue). The GEOFON data center, with its current 120 TB of data holdings (Figure 3), from over
144 4700 globally distributed stations, but with denser coverage in the focus areas of the GFZ, is one
145 of the largest seismological data archives in Europe.

146 Data management at the data center has substantially evolved in the last decade, as our focus
147 has shifted from the initial challenge of simply acquiring high-quality seismic data in standard
148 formats, towards better support of upstream data providers as well as provision of enhanced
149 standard services on the downstream part, in order to enable users from the research and
150 monitoring communities to deal with the challenges of big data.

151 The GEOFON data workflow distinguishes between real-time and temporary experiments. In the
152 case of real-time data, waveforms arrive via SeedLink protocol from ~1000 stations around the
153 world. Part of these data are used by our Rapid Earthquake Monitoring system for detection of
154 earthquakes and to provide event parametric data within a few minutes after origin time. The
155 full parametric data generated are stored in a database and made available to other institutions
156 engaged in earthquake monitoring in real-time (see section HMB – http message bus) and to
157 users via our web pages and other related services (see section The Rapid Earthquake
158 Information). Seismic waveforms acquired in real-time from streams for which GEOFON is the
159 authoritative data management center are ingested into our archive the day after they are
160 acquired, while the ones used only for monitoring are kept for one year in order to be able to
161 reproduce (or improve) our results.

162 In the case of temporary experiments, data providers can submit their data in miniSEED format
163 by means of the mseed2dmc client (see Data and Resources). In parallel to the data submission,
164 GEOFON staff work with principal investigators (PI) to generate high quality metadata. This
165 includes the registration of the seismic network with the FDSN and the minting of a DOI (Evans
166 et al, 2015). Once data transmission is finished, basic quality checks are performed on data and
167 metadata. More recently the capability of streaming data from temporary experiments in real-
168 time has been added, where generally cellular networks are used for network connectivity (e.g.
169 Heit et al., this issue).

170 For all networks we calculate probabilistic power spectral density plots (PPSDs) using ObsPy
171 (Beyreuther et al., 2010). We also support PIs to document their datasets with a technical report
172 (e.g. Cesca et al., 2018) published by the GFZ Library and linked to the data set. To foster report
173 publications, which is a requirement for GIPP users, we developed a convenient online tool

174 called Report Generator (see Data and Resources), providing different templates and automated
175 procedures to create most of the standard content required in dataset reports such as station
176 distribution maps, station tables, and collections of PPSD plots from the available (meta)data.
177 Recently, we included the possibility to run more detailed tests to detect problems with the
178 (meta)data quality early by means of a semi-automatic tool called AutoStatsQ (Petersen et al.,
179 2018), where the focus is mainly on problems with gains and orientation. This is particularly
180 important for GEOFON, which has begun archiving of Ocean Bottom Seismometer (OBS) data
181 from the Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Bremerhaven (AWI) and GEOMAR, Kiel. For this type of data,
182 we follow the guidelines produced and published within the SERA project (see Data and
183 Resources) in collaboration with many other partners.

184 GEOFON's internal data policies and agreements with data providers foster the adoption of
185 open licenses (e.g. Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0, see Data and Resources) for datasets archived
186 at the data center. If an experiment has utilized instruments from GIPP, the PIs must agree in
187 advance to release data under a CC-BY 4.0 license, after the end of the embargo period, which
188 can be up to four years after the completion of the experiment (see Data and Resources). CC-BY
189 is also the recommended license for partners using their own equipment (e.g. universities)
190 requesting data management services from GEOFON.

191 The GEOFON archive is currently fully integrated into the GFZ computing center infrastructure
192 and is ready to be scaled up in case of sudden increases in demand for storage space driven by
193 emerging technologies such as Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) applications, Large-N passive
194 seismic experiments, etc. In addition to the two physical copies of data (mirrored, hot storage)
195 within the GFZ campus, a third copy is replicated at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

196 using iRODS/B2SAFE services (Moore, 2008), adopted within our participation in the European
197 projects EUDAT2020 and EOSC-hub.

198 All data available at the GEOFON data center are accessible through standard web services and
199 protocols (e.g. FDSN web services, SeedLink), through a graphical interface called WebDC3
200 (Bianchi et al., 2015), an in-house development also running in other EIDA data centers (see
201 Seismological Software and Data Access), and also through many widely-used client tools and
202 libraries (e.g. ObsPy, fdsnwscripts, Pyrocko). In Table 1 we list the services to access data and
203 products currently provided by GEOFON. In 2019 alone, GEOFON served 200 million requests
204 (38 TB) from the archive to more than 2700 users and 160 TB of real-time data to 300 users,
205 including a number of operational earthquake and tsunami warning centers demanding high
206 availability services.

207 Data that are still under a temporary embargo period can be accessed by means of the new
208 federated authentication and authorization system developed at GEOFON, which has been
209 adopted by EIDA (see Data and Resources). The system benefits from the B2ACCESS service
210 provided by the Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ), which allows users from any place to be
211 authenticated in EIDA with their existing institutional credentials (no new accounts are needed)
212 by acting as a bridge to the eduGAIN service (see Data and Resources), which follows the same
213 approach as the well-known eduroam Wi-Fi access authentication. This approach has many
214 benefits considering the new European General Data Protection Regulations (see GDPR in Data
215 and Resources), as almost no user information is kept in GEOFON systems. The PI has fine-
216 grained control over who can access the data, and archiving at GEOFON will relieve them from
217 having to take care of data distribution to their cooperating partners, encouraging quick archival
218 of acquired data.

219 When new data are added to the archive, predefined waveform metrics such as number and
220 length of gaps, percentage of data available, RMS, length of overlaps are calculated and stored
221 in a database for further use in the WFCatalog system (Trani et al, 2017). This system exposes an
222 API to query the calculated metrics, allowing the selection of data based on seismic waveform
223 features as well as sensor geolocations and temporal specifications. Users save time by means
224 of the system capability to provide information on the waveforms before requesting and
225 downloading data, and data centers make better use of their connectivity resources.

226 All access to data and metadata are logged to produce detailed statistics. This is made available
227 to the network operators through a Redmine content management system (see Data and
228 Resources) used to keep updated information on the operation of all networks. The statistics
229 are also used internally to improve our services and refine the planning of future infrastructure
230 needs (e.g. bandwidth, storage capacity and type).

231 In recent years, we have gained experience not only in the establishment of sustainable data
232 policies to support the FAIR principles (Wilkinson, et al., 2016; Findable, Accessible,
233 Interoperable, Reusable) for the data we manage, but also in the design and implementation of
234 workflows to improve data management.

235 In order to promote a culture of data citation and address the growing need to ensure that
236 seismic networks can be reliably cited (e.g. GEOFON Data Centre, 1993), together with other
237 data centers from the USA and Europe, we initiated and continuously foster within FDSN a set of
238 recommendations to adopt DOIs for seismic networks and related FDSN services (see Data and
239 Resources).

240 This initial effort to address and foster attribution continues within ORFEUS and other
241 discussion groups and forums, where we are promoting usage and adoption of various

242 persistent identifiers (PIDs) for seismological data and instrument management to enhance
243 findability. In particular, to easily find and track all instruments in use at the GIPP we established
244 in collaboration with the GFZ library a dedicated workflow to assign ePIC PIDs to instruments
245 (see Data and Resources). The schema implemented in the PID record was designed as a
246 multidisciplinary collaboration within a Working Group of the Research Data Alliance (RDA)
247 called PIDINST, with the aim to be interoperable with other pool operators and systems from
248 different disciplines (see Stocker et al., 2020 for details).

249 Our community standards ensure that seismic (meta)data are Accessible by means of open
250 protocols (see FDSN web services in Data and Resources), and also that Datacite metadata
251 associated with the seismic network DOI will be accessible.

252 All seismic (meta)data hosted at GEOFON are also Interoperable with other disciplines. A good
253 example of this is the participation in the EPOS project, where partners from our community are
254 working on reaching agreements to define common, standard vocabularies and ontologies
255 following FAIR principles.

256 Research data are Reusable if the description of essential, recommended, and optional
257 metadata elements are machine-readable and verifiable, its use should be easy and data should
258 be citable to sustain data sharing and recognize the value of data (Wilkinson et al, 2016). Key
259 concepts here are the data licensing, provenance associated with data, and usage of domain-
260 relevant community standards. From these requirements, full provenance of data is the only
261 point which cannot be completely fulfilled. However, an important milestone has been achieved
262 in that we now assign well-defined licenses governing the usage of data as explained above.

263 In the context of further ongoing European projects, we are prototyping additional services to
264 improve data discovery, facilitate its access, and stage data in computer facilities for later
265 processing.

266 Rapid Earthquake Information

267 Data streams from the GEOFON network as well as ~1000 additional stations worldwide are
268 processed in real-time to determine automatic location estimates for globally recorded
269 earthquakes. The resulting virtual network is the so-called GEOFON Extended Virtual Network
270 (see GEVN in Data and Resources) used to list and attribute the third-party data we use. Rapid
271 earthquake information is provided to a number of stakeholders: earthquake and tsunami
272 warning centers worldwide, governmental agencies, disaster management teams, news media
273 and scientists at the GFZ and elsewhere, as well as to the general public. Earthquake parameters
274 are distributed via e-mail, SMS, RSS news feeds, web services, web pages and GEOFON forum. A
275 popular web page is the Global Seismic Monitor (see Data and Resources) showing the latest
276 largest events in the world. On average ~5000 events and ~1000 moment tensor solutions are
277 published per year (Figure 4) and disseminated to the various stakeholders according to their
278 user profiles. GEOFON is a key nodal member of the European-Mediterranean Seismological
279 Centre (EMSC, Godey et al., 2006). All processing is based on the SeisComP software package
280 (Helmholtz-Centre Potsdam-GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences & gempa GmbH,
281 2008). The GEOFON rapid earthquake information is among the first disseminated in the
282 aftermath of large earthquakes worldwide. Events are published with minimal delay to the web
283 page, GEOFON forum and RSS feeds whereas sms and email alerts dissemination takes place
284 within typically ~10 minutes (Figure 5).

285 Aiming at reducing the publication delay we teamed up with EMSC and the Hungarian Academy
286 of Sciences and developed a novel approach for early detection of felt events (Steed et al, 2019)
287 that combines crowdsourced data from EMSC with our automatic seismic detections. In the
288 initial test data set this approach reduced the publication delay from 3 minutes to 1.7 minutes
289 (median value). This development has been facilitated by the development of the HMB software
290 (Heinloo, 2016) that allowed GEOFON to stream real-time parametric information to EMSC. In
291 addition, GEOFON also provides high quality moment tensor solutions for major earthquakes
292 (Figure 4c and 4d).

293 [Seismological Software](#)

294 The GEOFON program has a long history of open software development for the community. In
295 many cases, software products developed here have been broadly adopted by the users.
296 Nowadays, GEOFON provides not only high quality software for seismological purposes, but also
297 for topics like high performance communication systems and data management. Here we
298 mention only a selection of our software products.

299

300 [SeisComP](#)

301 The GEOFON operations, spanning from the remote seismic stations to the rapid earthquake
302 information through the data center are based on the SeisComP® software package (Helmholtz
303 Centre Potsdam GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences and gempa GmbH 2008).
304 SeisComP features waveform data acquisition, distribution, quality control, archival and analysis
305 in real-time. Graphical user interfaces are available for configuration, manual event revision,
306 event display and state-of-health monitoring (Figure 6a and b).

307 The software has been developed within the GFZ since 2005 as part of the GITEWS project, as
308 described in the Introduction, and since 2009 a newly founded spin-off company of the GFZ,
309 gempa GmbH, started to further develop the package, together with tailor made solutions for
310 users. Several important additional modules were either developed by external contributors or
311 funded by them. Because of its accessible GUI, powerful back-end and the fact that its use was
312 free for non-commercial users it has become a widely-used package for seismological data
313 acquisition, data processing and data exchange. Within the context of several major Pan-
314 European infrastructure projects coordinated by ORFEUS (e.g. MEREDIAN, NERIES, NERA), major
315 developments in European seismology, in particular the VEBSN (Virtual European Broadband
316 Seismological Network), EIDA (European Integrated Data Archive) and RRSN (Rapid Strong
317 Motion Portal) could be achieved more easily by building on the SeisComP software platform,
318 which is in use at most European data centers. In the context of the GITEWS project, the
319 software architecture was from the onset designed to meet the stringent requirements of a
320 24/7 tsunami early warning center. Since the first public release in 2008 more than 500
321 SeisComP Public Licenses (SPL) have been released to institutions world-wide. This includes
322 many earthquake and tsunami warning operational centers e.g. ETHZ-SED (Switzerland), CEA
323 (France), GNS (New Zealand), GA (Australia), and BMKG (Indonesia), which also contributed to
324 further develop SeisComP in collaboration with gempa.

325 In April 2020, SeisComP (version 4) was released with major upgrades in core software
326 components and more comprehensive documentation. The most important change has been
327 the move from the SPL license to the standard GNU Affero Public License (AGPL), which now
328 allows both non-commercial and commercial users to freely use the software without the need

329 to apply for a license, and makes it more attractive for seismological software developers to
330 contribute to the code-base or develop plug-ins.

331

332 [WebDC3](#)

333 WebDC3 (Bianchi et al., 2015) is a web interface working on top of the FDSN standard web
334 services (Figure 6c). It is AJAX-based and allows users to conveniently discover seismic stations
335 and explore events in seismic catalogues, build and submit requests for data and metadata and
336 finally download the results in different formats. Requests can be built using either absolute
337 time windows or by station-event combinations suitable for different data processing pipelines.
338 Furthermore, construction of data requests and the actual download can be separated, allowing
339 for larger requests, in particular for users with low bandwidth or unstable connections.

340 Two operational modes are available, either as a front end to a single data center offering their
341 data holdings, or as a front end to a federation of data centers, giving access to data holdings
342 from all data centers federated by a Routing Service instance (see Routing Service below).

343 WebDC3 is available as an open-source package and has been adopted by a number of seismic
344 agencies including KNMI (Netherlands), SED (Switzerland), NIEP (Romania), NOA (Greece), KOERI
345 (Turkey), USP (Brazil), and BMKG (Indonesia).

346

347 [Fdsnws scripts](#)

348 fdsnwsscripts (see Data and Resources) is a collection of distributed data request clients that are
349 based on FDSN web services (fdsnws-station, fdsnws-dataselect) and the EIDA Routing Service

350 (Quinteros, 2017). The client tools in this development provide seismic waveform data in
351 miniSEED format and seismic metadata in Station XML.

352 The main tool of the package is `fdsnws_fetch`, conceived as a straightforward replacement for
353 the classic `arlink_fetch`, which was a distributed request tool making use of the Arlink
354 protocol. This tool not only provides backward compatibility, but also supports all new services
355 and functionalities offered within the EIDA and FDSN ecosystems. For user convenience and
356 easier integration into existing workflows, it accepts various legacy input formats, such as
357 `arlink_fetch` and `BREQ_FAST`. Based on the request content, in addition to delivering data and
358 metadata, the formal citation string including authors and DOIs to be included in manuscripts is
359 provided to the user, thus encouraging wider adoption of recommended data citation practices.

360 Other types of request clients are also included in the package. For instance, a specialized client,
361 `fdsnws2sds`, supporting requests for very large continuous datasets (including the capability to
362 resume downloads) and another one, `fdsnws2seed`, providing data in the legacy SEED format.

363

364 [Routing Service](#)

365 The Routing Service (Quinteros, 2017) is a service to federate data centers by integrating
366 multiple sources offering access to data and products using compatible types of services. This
367 service is a core service of the current EIDA infrastructure, a schematic view of the service is
368 provided in Figure 6d.

369 Examples of standard data and product objects are seismic time-series waveforms and station
370 inventories, but operators can optionally include other services with a similar interface (stream
371 codes and time windows), for instance WFCatalog, the web service providing quality control
372 metrics, which has been adopted by all EIDA data centers (Trani et al, 2017).

373 This routing service is supported by many popular clients in the community, like ObsPy
374 (Beyreuther et al., 2010), `fdsnws_fetch` and `WebDC3` among others.

375

376 [HMB – http message bus](#)

377 HMB (Heinloo, 2016) is a general-purpose message bus, which has been designed to be
378 compatible with SeisComP. It has been developed to distribute objects, such as event
379 detections, in real-time. HMB supports any objects that can be expressed in JSON or BSON
380 formats, including all SeisComP data model objects and even binary data, such as waveform
381 records. HMB is based on HTTP and works with all standard web servers. It is the core of the
382 real-time exchange process between GEOFON and other institutions (e.g. EMSC, BMKG, USGS-
383 NEIC) regarding parametric information (locations, magnitudes and amplitudes) from our
384 monitoring system.

385 [Conclusions and future challenges](#)

386 Since its inception, GEOFON has been promoting the open distribution of seismological data and
387 software as well as the development and adoption of standards, following the FDSN guiding
388 principles. Decades of efforts in this direction paved the road to data FAIRness in seismology at
389 GEOFON.

390 The GEOFON Global Seismic network, initially used as a vehicle for networking in order to
391 improve open data exchange and standardization, is today our backbone network for real-time
392 monitoring and for technical developments. Extension towards other observables (GNSS,
393 environmental parameters) is ongoing at selected stations, and their integration, in addition to
394 the modernization of legacy instruments, will remain a challenging task for the decade to come.

395 The GFZ seismological data center operated by GEOFON offers a secure place for GFZ's own
396 data and those of its partners, with data policies that implement the recommendations of
397 international initiatives within and beyond seismology (e.g., FDSN, RDA). The exponential
398 growth of data volume driven by technological innovation is a challenge that we will need to
399 address in the near future. Leveraging on EU funded projects, we are developing novel data
400 management strategies for emerging technologies such as DAS, cost effective micro sensors for
401 the Internet of Things (IoT), and other devices enabling dense observations. This is not only
402 challenging in the context of existing seismological data curation and distribution paradigms
403 (Quinteros et al., this issue), but also needs to be taken into account during data collection
404 where new efficient acquisition and transmission protocols are also needed. The SeedLink
405 transmission protocol will need to be enhanced to cope with these new needs, and discussions
406 on this have already begun.

407 Rapid earthquake information distributed by GEOFON are among the fastest available after
408 large earthquakes worldwide. The parametric earthquake information is distributed in real-time
409 to various stakeholders spanning from tsunami warning centers to the general public. We are
410 working towards extending the offer of earthquake related products, leveraging on internal
411 expertise available at GFZ, both technical and scientific.

412 The competences gained through the years in seismological software development for both
413 real-time applications and data management have enabled us to make progress with the
414 challenges listed above. In addition, the excellent networking within and outside GFZ and
415 Germany will facilitate integration and cooperation with other institutions and topics.

416 We remain engaged in knowledge and technology transfer as we consider this an important
417 component of our service portfolio to ensure sustainability of our activities. We do this in

418 synergy with the GFZ International Training Course and participate in a number of additional
419 outreach and/or training events. We also work closely together with the Public Relations
420 department of the GFZ to improve public understanding of earthquakes, in particular after
421 damaging or noteworthy events, and support the school lab of the GFZ to produce learning
422 materials (e.g., a recent outreach product showing global seismicity, focal mechanisms and
423 hazard).

424 The GEOFON Program, initially inspired by the idea of Rebeur-Paschwitz proposing a global
425 network of seismometers to monitor earthquakes, has drastically evolved through the years
426 since inception. The program began after the first disruptive wave of changes in seismology of
427 the 1980's and played a lead role in important developments for the global and European
428 communities. The program's work on SeedLink, SeisComP, and EIDA provided the technical
429 know-how to realize the first prototype of the modern seismological "Cloud". Seismology and
430 geoscience in general are currently going through the second disruptive wave of changes with
431 Big Data and Artificial Intelligence. FAIR GEOFON data and services facilitate the work of the
432 next generation of scientists to unveil new scientific discoveries that might be hidden in the
433 massive data holdings spanning several decades.

434 Data and Resources

435 All links in this section were last accessed in October 2020.

- 436 ● The GEOFON Program home page: <https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/>
- 437 ● ORFEUS home page can be found in <https://www.orfeus-eu.org/>.
- 438 ● IRIS home page can be found in <https://www.iris.edu/>.
- 439 ● InaTEWS: https://inatews.bmkg.go.id/en_index.php

- 440 ● The GEOFON Rapid earthquake monitoring system is available at <http://geofon.gfz->
- 441 potsdam.de/eqinfo/.
- 442 ● Documentation about the SeedLink protocol and server can be found at
- 443 <https://www.seiscomp.de/doc/apps/seedlink.html>.
- 444 ● International Training Course: [https://www.gfz-potsdam.de/en/about-us/education-](https://www.gfz-potsdam.de/en/about-us/education-and-training/seismology-and-hazard-assessment/)
- 445 [and-training/seismology-and-hazard-assessment/](https://www.gfz-potsdam.de/en/about-us/education-and-training/seismology-and-hazard-assessment/).
- 446 ● miniseed2dmc client can be found at <https://github.com/iris-edu/miniseed2dmc>
- 447 ● Detailed information about the different Creative Commons Licenses can be found in
- 448 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>.
- 449 ● The Report Generator can be found in its Github repository at
- 450 <https://github.com/rizac/gfzreport>.
- 451 ● The SERA Deliverable “Metadata challenges and proposed solutions” by Clinton, et al.
- 452 (2018) can be downloaded from <http://www.sera->
- 453 [eu.org/export/sites/sera/home/.galleries/Deliverables/SERA_D4.2_Metadata-challenges-and-](http://www.sera-eu.org/export/sites/sera/home/.galleries/Deliverables/SERA_D4.2_Metadata-challenges-and-proposed-solutions.pdf)
- 454 [proposed-solutions.pdf](http://www.sera-eu.org/export/sites/sera/home/.galleries/Deliverables/SERA_D4.2_Metadata-challenges-and-proposed-solutions.pdf).
- 455 ● GIPP terms of use: <https://www.gfz->
- 456 [potsdam.de/fileadmin/gfz/sec22/pdf_doc/GIPP/rules_GIPP_10_2019.pdf](https://www.gfz-potsdam.de/fileadmin/gfz/sec22/pdf_doc/GIPP/rules_GIPP_10_2019.pdf)
- 457 ● The Federated EIDA Authentication-Authorization software can be accessed at
- 458 <https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/eas>.
- 459 ● Information about the B2ACCESS service can be found at
- 460 <https://www.eudat.eu/services/b2access>.
- 461 ● Information about eduGAIN, the interederation service that connects identity
- 462 federations around the world, can be found at <https://edugain.org/>.

- 463 ● Information on the current General Data Protection Regulation can be found at
464 <https://gdpr.eu/>.
- 465 ● Redmine software and documentation can be seen at <https://www.redmine.org/>.
- 466 ● The “FDSN recommendations for seismic network DOIs and related FDSN services” has
467 been published with doi: 10.7914/D11596.
- 468 ● Information about the Handle system can be found in
469 https://www.handle.net/hnr_documentation.html.
- 470 ● Information about ePIC PIDs can be found in <https://www.pidconsortium.net/>.
- 471 ● Specifications of the FDSN web services can be found at
472 <http://www.fdsn.org/webservices/FDSN-WS-Specifications-1.2.pdf>.
- 473 ● Detailed information about the GEOFON Extended Virtual Network (GEVN) can be read
474 at <https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/eqinfo/gevn/>.
- 475 ● Information about the B2SAFE service can be found at
476 <https://www.eudat.eu/services/b2safe>.
- 477 ● Information of the EOSC-hub project (Integrating and managing services for the
478 European Open Science Cloud) and for the EUDAT project (Collaborative Data Infrastructure) are
479 available at <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/> and <https://eudat.eu/> respectively.
- 480 ● Documentation about the Rapid Raw Strong Motion Portal (RRSM) is available at
481 <https://www.orfeus-eu.org/opencms/rrsm/information/>.
- 482 ● Information about fdsnwscripts can be found in [https://geofon.gfz-](https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/software/fdsnws_scripts/)
483 [potsdam.de/software/fdsnws_scripts/](https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/software/fdsnws_scripts/).
- 484 ● Detailed and updated documentation of the Routing Service is publicly available at
485 <https://routing.readthedocs.io/>.

486 • Poster for the School lab (in German) can be found at [https://www.gfz-](https://www.gfz-
487 potsdam.de/en/media-and-communication/current-earthquake-information/)

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622 Tables

623 Table 1: List of GEOFON services with name, entry point and description.

Name	Location / entry point	Description
fdsnws-station	http://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/fdsnws/station/1/	Provide metadata information for the data in archive in text and XML formats (EIDA service)
fdsnws-dataselect	http://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/fdsnws/dataselect/1/	Waveform data provisioning system (archive) in mseed format (EIDA service)
SeedLink	geofon.gfz-potsdam.de:18000	Real-time waveform data provisioning system in mseed format
WFCatalog	http://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/eidaws/wfcatalog/1/	Quality metrics of seismic waveforms in archive (EIDA service)
WebDC3	http://eida.gfz-potsdam.de/	Graphical User Interface (GUI) to access GFZ and EIDA data holdings by

		events or absolut time
AAI	https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/eas	Authentication service (EIDA service)
EQinfo	https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/eqinfo/	Interactive access to Rapid Earthquake Information
fdsnws-event	http://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/fdsnws/event/1/	Event web service to access Rapid Earthquake Information (parametric data contributed to EMSC and ISC)
Routing Service	http://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/eidaws/routing/1/	Routes to GFZ data holdings and synchronization (EIDA service)
GEOFON forum	https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/forum/	Forum with News, updates on Big and XXL events and other topics
Redmine	https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/redmine/	GEOFON Program management and issue tracking tool (for stations

		and network operators only)
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624 [Figure captions](#)

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626 Figure 1: a) GEOFON real-time seismic stations. Red triangles indicate currently operational
627 stations, while former non-operational stations are indicated with reversed triangles in grey; b)
628 example of a GEOFON station (GE.SALP, Salfit, Palestinian territories). Left: solar power system
629 with the VSAT antenna used as primary communication channel. Right: acquisition rack with
630 digitizer, rugged PC to buffer data locally, VSAT modem, mobile router, controller for power
631 management and SOH. In the center the broadband sensor.

632

633 Figure 2: Schematic view of the GEOFON data center and its relation with the other GEOFON
634 components. Data from the GE network are flowing to the archive where they are curated and
635 used with all other real-time streams of the GEVN for the rapid earthquake information. Real-
636 time and historical data are served to users by means of SeedLink, FDSN web services and
637 WebDC3 between others.

638

639 Figure 3: a) distribution of the approximately 4790 stations archived at GEOFON (October 2020).
640 Permanent stations are plotted with inverted triangles, while temporary stations are shown
641 with normal triangles. b) data archive size by year of data acquisition and type of experiment
642 (permanent or temporary networks). The curve plotted in red indicates the fraction of strong-
643 motion data.

644

645 Figure 4: a) Distribution of earthquake locations published by GEOFON (2008-2019) by
646 magnitude (size) and depth (color). b) Frequency magnitude distribution for all events published
647 2016-2019. The line shows the cumulative distribution, the histogram the number of
648 earthquakes in each 0.1 magnitude bin. Revised means that a human analyst has either
649 confirmed this event or added or removed picks manually. c) Moment tensors calculated by
650 GEOFON 2011-2019 (only $M_w \geq 5.5$ events shown for clarity). Red: thrust events, Green: Strike-
651 slip, Blue: normal, Gray: oblique. Yellow-orange line shows plate boundaries after Bird (2003). d)
652 Frequency magnitude distribution for all moment tensors published 2016-2019. The line shows
653 the cumulative distribution, the histogram the number of earthquakes in each 0.1 magnitude
654 bin.

655

656 Figure 5: Time elapsed since origin time for first automatic publication of events on the web site
657 (blue) and for alerting subscribed users (green) via SMS, Email or the GEOFON Forum. Numbers
658 are for 2019.

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660 Figure 6. Screenshots of modules of the SeisComP software: a) origin locator view (scolv); b) the
661 picker. c) Screenshot of the WebDC3 software and d) schema of the routing service.

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